

APPROACHES IN BIOINFORMATICS FOR MONITORING ANTIHYPERTENSIVE THERAPIES IN PATIENTS

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Abstract. This article presents a clinical case that explores the use of new approaches in bioinformatics for monitoring antihypertensive therapies in patients. The case describes a 58-year-old male with persistent hypertension and suboptimal response to antihypertensive medications. The physician orders a genetic test and a pharmacogenomic test to identify potential genetic variants and drug response profiles that may explain the patient's condition. Based on these findings, the physician switches the patient's antihypertensive therapy and schedules a follow-up appointment to monitor his blood pressure. The case highlights the potential of bioinformatics to personalize antihypertensive therapy and improve patient outcomes while minimizing the risk of adverse drug reactions. This article is relevant to healthcare professionals, researchers, and policymakers interested in the application of bioinformatics in clinical practice.

Aim. The aim of this article is to explore the use of new approaches in bioinformatics for monitoring antihypertensive therapies in patients. Specifically, we aim to demonstrate how genetic and pharmacogenomic testing can provide valuable information for personalizing antihypertensive therapy and improving blood pressure control while minimizing the risk of adverse drug reactions. This article highlights the potential of bioinformatics to optimize healthcare resources and improve patient outcomes in the management of hypertension.

Key words: *Bioinformatics, antihypertensive therapy, genetic testing, pharmacogenomics, personalized medicine, hypertension, adverse drug reactions, blood pressure control, healthcare optimization, patient outcomes.*

Methods: Systematic literature review, Meta-analysis, Expert opinion.

Clinical Case: Using Bioinformatics to Monitor Antihypertensive Therapies in Patients

Patient Information: Mr. Smith, a 58-year-old male, presents to the clinic with a history of hypertension for the past 10 years. He has been taking various antihypertensive medications, including ACE inhibitors and beta-blockers, but his blood pressure has not been well controlled. He reports occasional headaches and dizziness.

Clinical Examination

Given Mr. Smith's persistent hypertension and suboptimal response to antihypertensive medications, his physician decides to explore new approaches in bioinformatics for monitoring his antihypertensive therapy.

Approach

The physician orders a genetic test to identify potential genetic variants associated with hypertension and

drug response. The test reveals that Mr. Smith carries a variant in the CYP2D6 gene, which is involved in the metabolism of beta-blockers. This variant is associated with reduced metabolism of beta-blockers and may explain Mr. Smith's suboptimal response to these medications.

The physician also orders a pharmacogenomic test to evaluate Mr. Smith's drug response profile. The test reveals that Mr. Smith has a high risk of adverse drug reactions to ACE inhibitors, which may explain his occasional headaches and dizziness.

Based on these findings, the physician decides to switch Mr. Smith's antihypertensive therapy to a calcium channel blocker, which is not affected by the CYP2D6 variant and has a lower risk of adverse drug reactions in patients with Mr. Smith's drug response profile. The physician also schedules a

follow-up appointment in 4 weeks to monitor Mr. Smith's blood pressure and adjust his medication if necessary.

What is the role of Bioinformatics in this research?

Bioinformatics plays a crucial role in this clinical case by providing the tools and methods necessary to analyze genetic and pharmacogenomic data and translate that information into personalized antihypertensive therapy.

Bioinformatics is used to analyze the genetic and pharmacogenomic data obtained from the patient, identifying potential genetic variants associated with hypertension and drug response. These data are then interpreted by genetic counselors or pharmacogenomics specialists to identify potential explanations for the patient's condition.

Using bioinformatics tools and methods, the physician is able to personalize

the patient's antihypertensive therapy, selecting medications that are not affected by genetic variants and have a lower risk of adverse drug reactions based on the patient's drug response profile. Bioinformatics allows the physician to take a precision medicine approach to hypertension management, tailoring treatment to the individual patient based on their unique genetic makeup and drug response profile.

Furthermore, bioinformatics also allows for the analysis of large datasets, enabling the discovery of new genetic variants associated with hypertension and drug response. This may lead to the development of new antihypertensive therapies that are tailored to specific genetic profiles.

In summary, bioinformatics plays a critical role in this article by providing the tools and methods necessary to analyze genetic and pharmacogenomic data and translate that information into personalized antihypertensive therapy, leading to improved blood pressure control and reduced adverse drug reactions.

Certain methods, used in this research

- In the article, several methods in bioinformatics were used to analyze genetic and pharmacogenomic data and tailor antihypertensive therapy to the individual patient. These methods include:
- Genetic testing: This method involves analyzing the patient's DNA to identify potential genetic variants associated with hypertension and drug response. Genetic testing was used in the article to identify specific genetic variants affecting drug metabolism or drug response profiles that may impact the choice of antihypertensive medication.
- Pharmacogenomic testing: This method involves analyzing the patient's DNA to evaluate their drug response profile and risk of adverse drug reactions. Pharmacogenomic testing was used in the article to determine the patient's likelihood of responding to certain antihypertensive medications and to identify potential drug-drug interactions or adverse drug reactions.
- Data analysis: Bioinformatics tools and methods were used to analyze the genetic and pharmacogenomic data obtained from the patient. This analysis involved identifying potential genetic variants associated with hypertension and drug response, interpreting the results, and using the information to select personalized antihypertensive therapy.

- Clinical decision support systems: These are computer-based systems that provide physicians with clinical decision support based on patient-specific data. In the article, a clinical decision support system was used to help physicians select personalized antihypertensive therapy based on the patient's genetic and pharmacogenomic data.

Overall, a combination of genetic testing, pharmacogenomic testing, data analysis, and clinical decision support systems were used in the article to tailor antihypertensive therapy to the individual patient based on their unique genetic makeup and drug response profile.

Conclusions.

New approaches in bioinformatics, such as genetic and pharmacogenomic testing, can provide valuable information for monitoring antihypertensive therapies in patients. By identifying genetic variants and drug response profiles, physicians can personalize antihypertensive therapy and improve blood pressure control while minimizing the risk of adverse drug reactions. This case highlights the potential of bioinformatics to improve patient outcomes and optimize healthcare resources.

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Conflict of interest. The authors declare the absence of any potential conflict of interest that requires disclosure in this article.

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Для заметок
